

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

AN OVERVIEW OF KEY FEATURES OF A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER USING THE RULES OF REFERENCE FOR RESPONSE AND MAJOR PAPERS AT EUCLID AS THE CASE STUDY

1) INTRODUCTION

In a broad sense, academic papers are written to convey a convincing notion to the readers based on verifiable facts. In achieving that objective, they generally follow universally accepted norms of research entailing logical sequence of structure, starting with the establishment of a proposition, addressed through factual answers from which a conclusion is drawn.

2) RUDIMENTARY APPROACH TO A RESEARCH PAPER

A sound paper requires a thorough assessment of the validity of the research hypothesis, the conceptual intricacies of which are elucidated by assembling relevant information that responds to the research question (Euclid ACA-401 Course pack, Period 1). As opposed to other forms of writing, academic work does not merely seek to document facts relating to a particular subject matter, they show a common pattern of developing arguments supported by facts articulated through a coherent structure (Ibid). In effect, having collected the appropriate data, such information could be critically vital to visualizing an initial approach to the research question. This approach will thus set the trajectory to unpacking the labyrinth of issues entailed in the research problem (Ibid). Hence, in responding to the problem, the writer's investigation must reflect ideas from existing

work of other researchers. It follows therefore that undertaking an effective academic research project necessitates the researcher to carefully run through related texts, because the process of investigation provides the conceptual lens through which views are advanced (Euclid ACA-401 Course pack, Period 1).

Moreover, to achieve that objective, note taking is a vital component to the research process. Ideally, this could be done during the second reading of the material in question. While paraphrasing key supporting evidence to the research topic, it is plausible to retain a firm grasp of the research question to be answered. Assembling valid evidence to the research could take the shape of making summary of, or extracting verbatim texts, or quantitative statistics of relevant information to the topic (Euclid ACA-401 Course pack, Period 1).

However, while the presentation of facts is considered as a necessary feature of a good academic research, the submission of a balanced view of the subject cannot be overemphasized. This alludes to the responsibility of the writer to examine a broad range of views of writers that differ and concur with the topic being examined. Explaining the rationality of one writer over another and highlighting its bearing on the conclusion reached in an essay is a key feature of a standard academic work.

Furthermore, in order to present a coherent flow of an essay, its structure must entail an introduction setting the tune of the subject with a broad opening statement; the body providing answers to the research question backed by a logical empirical discussion. Invariably, the essay ends with a conclusion presenting a summary of key issues with an emphatic statement relating to the ramifications of the findings.

Nonetheless, writing a good research paper do not solely depend on the writer's attempt to develop the course of his argument paying heed to the accepted form or structure. A sound research paper must be free of all traces of plagiarism, which *inter alia* suggests that all sources consulted in the work must be properly recognized (Ibid). As a corollary requirement to students pursuing a specific course of study, they must do so keeping in mind the mandated institutional preference for citations (Euclid ACA-401 Course pack, Period 1).

Additionally, in writing an academic research paper, a key characteristic of sound paper is consistency in both style and the American or the United Kingdom English and punctuation. Much as there is no strict requirement for choosing one over the other, the common practice is to stick to one of them for the purpose of overall consistency in the work being undertaken.

3) HIGHLIGHTS OF MANDATED REFERENCE STYLE FOR RESPONSE AND MAJOR PAPERS FOR EUCLID'S STUDENTS

As a result, the Turabian style of referencing and (or) the Blue book styles have been specified as the required citation format to be used by Euclid's scholars pursuing a programme in the legal field (Euclid's initial student orientation handout 2019), 2. In terms of work on 'Response Papers' at Euclid, the in-text (parenthetical) citation style is recommended with a full list of sources consulted outlined in the bibliography. With regards to referencing sources used in 'Major Papers', the footnote style of citation accompanied by a comprehensive list of references in the form of a bibliography is the appropriate reference approach to use (Ibid).

However, it is worth mentioning that while the two approaches are the recommended formats for writing 'Response and Major Papers', it is important to highlight the nuances in citations from books in the context of the broader Chicago reference style also construed as the Turabian reference style. Citations from books with one, two or four and more authors differ significantly because their forms in the in-text and footnote/bibliographic styles are conventionally different. In in-text citations from books with a single author, the last name of the author, the year of publication and the page number where applicable is all that is required for citation. In similar fashion, with citations from books with two authors, the last name of the two authors, the year of publication and the page number are the features essential for parenthetical citations. In instances where a book is authored by four or more writers, only the surname of the first author followed by the Latin abbreviation 'et al' or 'and others' including the year of publication and page number is required. In situations where a citation is to be made from the same source which has been immediately stated, it takes the form using the Latin words 'ibidem' and 'eadem' which are abbreviated in a parenthetical citation as 'ib' or 'ibid' and 'ead' for male and female authors respectively ((Euclid ACA-401 Course pack, Period 1).

On the other hand, it is essential to point out that citations in a bibliographic list of references at the end of an academic paper, provides for the observation of some basic rules, but for the purpose of brevity, few of these rules have been discussed. For the specific purpose of spotlighting Euclid's mandated approach in writing some papers, it is necessary to mention that the university obliges students writing for 'Major Papers' to use the footnote style using at least three footnotes for every page (Euclid's initial student orientation handout 2019), 6. Unlike the parenthetical style, the footnote style subscribes to stating the full name of the author(s) (keeping in mind rules earlier explained about multiple authors), followed by the title of the work, the place of publication, the publisher and the year of publication ("On its website, the Turabian Style: In-Text (Parenthetical) Citations and Reference List ..."). Whereas the footnote style of referencing bind students to mention the work title, place of publication, publisher and the year including the page number, it maintains the same rule as in the list of bibliography, except that the places of commas in the footnotes switch sides with Periods in the bibliographic

reference. Despite the difference in referencing ‘Response and Major Papers’, a similar thread running through the two forms is that both conform to the same pattern of list in the bibliography.

4) CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, it suffices to note that in writing research papers, the sequential presentation of evidenced-based facts, supported by the appropriate style of reference, are indispensable characteristics for any good essay. I would therefore emphasize the point that no research work can meet the threshold of accepted norms if it does not square with the rules of proper referencing.

REFERENCES

1. Euclid ACA-401 Course Pack, Period 1.
2. Turabian Style: In-Text (Parenthetical) Citations and Reference List.<http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-in-text-parenthetical-citations--reference-list> (accessed May,18 2019).
3. TurabianStyle:Footnotes/Endnotes&Bibliography.<http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-footnotesendnotes—bibliography> (accessed May,18 2019).
4. (Euclid’s initial student orientation handout 2019, 2).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.